

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**VALIDATED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS
ESTIMATION OF ASPIRIN AND CLOPIDOGREL IN BULK
AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM**

Sama Madhu, Alivelu Samala*, Dr.D. Venkata Ramana, Dr. Gadipally sai kiran

¹Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Holy Mary Institute Of Technology And Science
(College Of Pharmacy), Kondapur Telangana.

Article Received: July 2024

Accepted: August 2024

Published: September 2024

Abstract:

A rapid and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous determination of Clopidogrel and Aspirin in pure forms and tablet dosage forms. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Sunfire C18 column with a mobile phase consisting of a mixture of water and acetonitrile (60:40% v/v) at a flow rate of 0.9 ml/min. Detection was performed at 220 nm, and the retention times were 3.0 min for Aspirin and 3.8 ± 0.02 min for Clopidogrel. The method exhibited linear responses over concentration ranges of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Aspirin and 75-375 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Clopidogrel, with method precision below 2.0% RSD (Relative Standard Deviation).

The validated RP-HPLC method is suitable and effective for quality control analysis of both bulk drugs and pharmaceutical formulations containing Aspirin and Clopidogrel. Its robustness, demonstrated by precise quantification and low variability, underscores its applicability in routine quality assurance practices. With straightforward chromatographic conditions and rapid analysis times, this method offers a practical solution for ensuring the consistency and potency of pharmaceutical products. Therefore, it is recommended for implementation in pharmaceutical laboratories dedicated to maintaining regulatory compliance and product quality standards. method is useful in the quality control of bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords Aspirin, Clopidogrel, RP-HPLC, validation.**Corresponding author:****Alivelu Samala,**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
Holy Mary Institute of Technology and Science,
Kondapur, Telangana.Email Id- s.alivelu@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Alivelu Samala et al Validated RP-HPLC Method For Simultaneous Estimation Of Aspirin And Clopidogrel In Bulk And Tablet Dosage Form., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (9).

INTRODUCTION:

Analysis may be defined as the science and art of determining the composition of materials in terms of the elements or compounds contained in them. In fact, analytical chemistry is the science of chemical identification and determination of the composition (atomic, molecular) of substances, materials and their chemical structure.

Chemical compounds and metallic ions are the basic building blocks of all biological structures and processes which are the basis of life. Some of these naturally occurring compounds and ions (endogenous species) are present only in very small amounts in specific regions of the body, while others such as peptides, proteins, carbohydrates, lipids and nucleic acids are found in all parts of the body. The main object of analytical chemistry is to develop scientifically substantiated methods that allow the qualitative and quantitative evaluation of materials with certain accuracy. Analytical chemistry derives its principles from various branches of science like chemistry, physics, microbiology, nuclear science and electronics. This method provides information about the relative amount of one or more of these components. [1]

Every country has legislation on bulk drugs and their pharmaceutical formulations that sets standards and obligatory quality indices for them. These regulations are presented in separate articles relating to individual drugs and are published in the form of book called "Pharmacopoeia" (e.g. IP, USP, and BP). Quantitative chemical analysis is an important tool to assure that the raw material used and the intermediate products meet the required specifications. Every year number of drugs is introduced into the market. Also quality is important in every product or service, but it is vital in medicines as it involves life.

There is a time lag from the date of introduction of a drug into the market to the date of its inclusion in pharmacopoeias. This happens because of the possible uncertainties in the continuous and wider usage of these drugs, report of new toxicities and development of patient resistance and introduction of better drugs by the competitors. Under these conditions standard and analytical procedures for these drugs may not be available in Pharmacopoeias. In instrumental analysis, a physical property of the substance is measured to determine its chemical composition. Pharmaceutical analysis comprises those procedures necessary to determine the identity, strength, quality and purity of substances of therapeutic importance. [2]

Pharmaceutical analysis deals not only with medicaments (drugs and their formulations) but also with their precursors i.e. with the raw material on which degree of purity and quality of medicament depends. The quality of the drug is determined after establishing its authenticity by testing its purity and the quality of pure substance in the drug and its formulations.

Quality control is a concept which strives to produce a perfect product by series of measures designed to prevent and eliminate errors at different stages of production. The decision to release or reject a product is based on one or more type of control action. With the growth of pharmaceutical industry during last several years, there has been rapid progress in the field of pharmaceutical analysis involving complex instrumentation. Providing simple analytical procedure for complex formulation is a matter of most importance. So, it becomes necessary to develop new analytical methods for such drugs. In brief the reasons for the development of newer methods of drugs analysis are:

1. The drug or drug combination may not be official in any pharmacopoeias.
2. A proper analytical procedure for the drug may not be available in the literature due to Patent regulations.
3. Analytical methods for a drug in combination with other drugs may not be available.
4. Analytical methods for the quantitation of the drug in biological fluids may not be available.
5. The existing analytical procedures may require expensive reagents and solvents. It may also involve cumbersome extraction and separation procedures and these may not be reliable. ^{1,2}

Different methods of analysis:

The following techniques are available for separation and analysis of components of interest.

Spectral methods:

The spectral techniques are used to measure electromagnetic radiation which is either absorbed or emitted by the sample.

E.g. UV-Visible spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy, NMR, ESR spectroscopy, Flame photometry, Fluorimetry.²

Electro analytical methods:

Electro analytical methods involved in the measurement of current voltage or resistance as a property of concentration of the component in solution mixture.

E.g. Potentiometry, Conductometry, Amperometry.²

Chromatographic methods

Chromatography is a technique in which chemicals in solutions travel down columns or over surface by means of liquids or gases and are separated from each other due to their molecular characteristics.

E.g. Paper chromatography, thin layer chromatography (TLC), High performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC), High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), Gas chromatography (GC).²

Miscellaneous Techniques

Mass Spectrometry, Thermal Analysis.

Hyphenated Techniques

GC-MS (Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry), LC-MS (Liquid Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry), ICP-MS (Inductivity Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry), GC-IR (Gas Chromatography – Infrared Spectroscopy), MS-MS (Mass Spectrometry – Mass Spectrometry).

INTRODUCTION TO HPLC:

HPLC is also called as high pressure liquid chromatography since high pressure is used to increase the flow rate and efficient separation by forcing the mobile phase through at much higher rate. The pressure is applied using a pumping system. The development of HPLC from classical column chromatography can be attributed to the development of smaller particle sizes. Smaller particle size is important since they offer more surface area over the conventional large particle sizes. The HPLC is the method of choice in the field of analytical chemistry, since this method is specific, robust, linear, precise and accurate and the limit of detection is low and also it offers the following advantages.

1. Improved resolution of separated substances
2. column packing with very small (3,5 and 10 μm) particles
3. Faster separation times (minutes)
4. Sensitivity
5. Reproducibility
6. continuous flow detectors capable of handling small flow rates
7. Easy sample recovery, handling and maintenance.⁶

Types of HPLC Techniques

Based on Modes of Chromatography

These distinctions are based on relative polarities of stationary and mobile phases

Reverse phase chromatography: In this the stationary phase is non-polar and mobile phase is polar. In this technique the polar compounds are eluted first and non polar compounds are retained in the column and eluted slowly. Therefore it is widely used technique.

Normal phase chromatography: In this the stationary phase is polar and mobile phase is non-polar. In this technique least polar compounds travel faster and are eluted first where as the polar compounds are retained in the column for longer time and eluted.⁴

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instruments used:

HPLC from WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA Detector.

Chemicals used:

Aspirin and Clopidogrel from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK), Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck.

Hplc method development:

Trails:

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Aspirin and Clopidogrel working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol. Further pipette 0.15ml of the Aspirin and 2.25ml of the Clopidogrel stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Validation

Preparation of mobile phase:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 600ml (60%) of Water, 400ml of Acetonitrile (40%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Mobile phase ratio : Acetonitrile:
Water (40:60v/v)

Column : Sunfire C18 Flow rate : 0.9ml/min
 (4.6×250mm) 5 μ Injection volume : 10 μ l
 Column temperature : 35°C Run time : 6minutes
 Wavelength : 220nm

Fig: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Aspirin	3.006	731322	61677	1.2	8574
2	Clopidogrel	3.853	3421257	319786	1.1	9664

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Fig.No.19: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Table No. 19: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Aspirin	3.005	658995	61772	1.1	7442
2	Clopidogrel	3.848	3096188	324054	1.2	7331

Acceptance criteria:

- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

Assay (Standard):**Table. 20: Peak results for assay standard of Aspirin**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Aspirin	3.008	658263	61335	7462	1.2
2	Aspirin	3.009	658264	61947	8264	1.1
3	Aspirin	3.008	653426	61049	6627	1.2
4	Aspirin	3.010	653058	61141	7264	1.1
5	Aspirin	3.006	657393	61735	6645	1.1
Mean			656080.8			
Std. Dev.			2618.946			
% RSD			0.39918			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table: Peak results for assay standard of Clopidogrel

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Clopidogrel	3.857	3028176	381011	9583	1.1
2	Clopidogrel	3.859	3018373	381645	8927	1.2
3	Clopidogrel	3.857	3018462	381663	8465	1.1
4	Clopidogrel	3.861	3081711	381746	9222	1.2
5	Clopidogrel	3.853	3075143	381193	8462	1.1
Mean			3044373			
Std. Dev.			31427.07			
% RSD			1.0323			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Assay (Sample):**Table: Peak results for Assay sample of Aspirin**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Aspirin	3.008	651712	61173	1.2	8563
2	Aspirin	3.005	657635	61936	1.1	7462
3	Aspirin	3.007	658917	61196	1.1	9264

Table: Peak results for Assay sample of Clopidogrel

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Clopidogrel	3.854	3029472	361938	1.1	6476
2	Clopidogrel	3.853	3017462	361746	1.1	7264
3	Clopidogrel	3.855	3028171	371864	1.2	6545

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Aspirin and Clopidogrel in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 100.1%

LINEARITY**CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR LINEARITY STUDY FOR ASPIRIN:**

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
5	230247
10	462332
15	659905
20	892989
25	1101075

Fig.No.: Chromatogram showing linearity level

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 8388. These values meet the validation criteria.

Chromatographic data for linearity study for clopidogrel:

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
75	1215225
150	2135937
225	3020839
300	4078841
375	5058145

Fig.No.40: Chromatogram showing linearity level

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 10151. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

Repeatability:

Table: Results of repeatability for Aspirin:

S. No	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Aspirin	3.003	654426	61521	8474	1.1
2	Aspirin	3.005	659862	61937	8262	1.2
3	Aspirin	3.007	650837	62018	8117	1.1
4	Aspirin	3.008	651433	61893	7917	1.2
5	Aspirin	3.005	652752	61867	8011	1.1
Mean			653862			
Std.dev			3626.323			
%RSD			0.554601			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table: Results of repeatability for Clopidogrel:

S. No	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Clopidogrel	3.851	3028371	381736	6881	1.1
2	Clopidogrel	3.852	3009188	380138	9363	1.2
3	Clopidogrel	3.854	3067464	386615	7844	1.1
4	Clopidogrel	3.853	3076611	380183	9746	1.2
5	Clopidogrel	3.851	3011912	379471	7883	1.2
Mean			3038709			
Std.dev			31463.69			
%RSD			1.035429			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Intermediate precision:

Day 1:

Table: Results of Intermediate precision day1 for Aspirin

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Aspirin	3.007	658911	60173	9141	1.1
2	Aspirin	3.005	650383	61936	9662	1.2
3	Aspirin	3.005	658813	60383	9746	1.1
4	Aspirin	3.005	651138	60774	7746	1.1
5	Aspirin	3.005	659937	61947	8264	1.2
6	Aspirin	3.010	653715	61893	7836	1.1
Mean			655482.8			
Std. Dev.			4258.945			
% RSD			0.649742			

Acceptance criteria:

%RSD of Six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table: Results of Intermediate precision day1 for Clopidogrel

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Clopidogrel	3.851	3021731	369771	8564	1.1
2	Clopidogrel	3.848	3019183	372746	9227	1.1
3	Clopidogrel	3.848	3029847	371866	7565	1.2
4	Clopidogrel	3.850	3028471	369017	7726	1.1
5	Clopidogrel	3.849	3088641	376453	6746	1.2
6	Clopidogrel	3.860	3056633	386621	5977	1.1
Mean			3040751			
Std. Dev.			26990.09			
% RSD			0.887613			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of Six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Day 2:**Table: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Aspirin**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Aspirin	3.006	648822	61847	6983	1.1
2	Aspirin	3.008	640863	59882	7728	1.2
3	Aspirin	3.008	643382	60774	9576	1.1
4	Aspirin	3.007	641884	58928	8275	1.2
5	Aspirin	3.007	647822	61483	9837	1.1
6	Aspirin	3.005	649181	60928	8744	1.2
Mean			645325.7			
Std. Dev.			3711.009			
% RSD			0.57506			

Acceptance criteria:

%RSD of Six different sample solutions should not more than 2 Table:

Table: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Clopidogrel

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Clopidogrel	3.853	3075833	389911	7039	1.1
2	Clopidogrel	3.857	3029583	379019	9857	1.2
3	Clopidogrel	3.854	3021991	381875	7881	1.1
4	Clopidogrel	3.855	3022485	391099	7902	1.2
5	Clopidogrel	3.854	3085833	389222	9285	1.1
6	Clopidogrel	3.853	3019482	391184	8955	1.2
Mean			3042535			
Std. Dev.			30022.42			
% RSD			0.986757			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of Six different sample solutions should not more than 2

ACCURACY:**Table: The accuracy results for Aspirin**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	331938	7.5	7.3	99.88	100.166
100%	658274	15	14.7	98.89	
150%	970963	22.5	22.2	101	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Table: The accuracy results for Clopidogrel

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	209357	112.5	112.3	99.7%	99%
100%	420697.7	225	224.7	99%	
150%	631550.7	337.5	337.4	99%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Table No. 38: Results for Robustness -Aspirin

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	658211	3.006	8793	1.2
Less Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	621077	3.441	7269	1.3
More Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	642190	2.663	9446	1.2
Less organic phase	542402	3.185	8126	1.1
More organic phase	642112	2.867	5854	1.3

Table No. 39: Results for Robustness-Clopidogrel

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	429069	3.853	5224	1.59
Less Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	472673	4.426	6328	1.58
More Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	392497	3.415	6217	1.54
Less organic phase	391379	4.291	6996	1.61
More organic phase	391703	3.583	6120	1.50

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

In this study, a rapid and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the determination of Clopidogrel and Aspirin in both their pure forms and tablet dosage forms. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Sunfire C18 column with a mobile phase consisting of a mixture of water and acetonitrile (60:40% v/v) at a flow rate of 0.9 ml/min. Detection was performed at 220 nm, and the retention times were found to be 3.0 min for Aspirin and 3.8 ± 0.02 min for Clopidogrel. The method demonstrated linear responses within the concentration ranges of 5-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Aspirin and 75-375 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Clopidogrel. Precision of the method, determined by assay, was below 2.0% RSD (Relative Standard Deviation). Overall, this validated RP-HPLC method proves to be suitable and effective for the quality control analysis of both bulk drugs and pharmaceutical formulations containing Aspirin and Clopidogrel.

The developed RP-HPLC method offers a robust and accurate means for the simultaneous quantification of Aspirin and Clopidogrel in various matrices including bulk substances and tablet formulations. The method's ability to provide precise results with low variability (below 2.0% RSD) indicates its suitability for routine quality control applications. By utilizing straightforward chromatographic conditions and achieving rapid analysis times, this method presents a practical solution for ensuring the potency and consistency of pharmaceutical products containing Aspirin and Clopidogrel.

Therefore, it can be confidently recommended for use in pharmaceutical laboratories engaged in quality assurance and regulatory compliance.

Acknowledgement:

The Authors are thankful to the Management and Principal, Department of Pharmacy, Holy Mary Institute of Technology and science (College of Pharmacy) in Kondapur, Telangana, for extending support to carry out the research work. Finally, the authors express their gratitude to the Sura Pharma Labs, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, for providing research equipment and facilities.

REFERENCES:

1. Dr. Kealey and P.J Haines, Analytical Chemistry, 1stedition, Bios Publisher, (2002), PP 1-7.
2. A.BraithWait and F.J.Smith, Chromatographic Methods, 5thedition, Kluwer Academic Publisher, (1996), PP 1-2.
3. Andrea Weston and Phyllis. Brown, HPLC Principle and Practice, 1st edition, Academic press, (1997), PP 24-37.
4. Yuri Kazakevich and Rosario Lobrutto, HPLC for Pharmaceutical Scientists, 1stedition, Wiley Interscience A JohnWiley & Sons, Inc., Publication, (2007), PP 15-23.
5. Chromatography, (online). URL:<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chromatography>.
6. Meyer V.R. Practical High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, 4th Ed. England, John Wiley & Sons Ltd, (2004), PP 7-8.
7. Sahajwalla CG a new drug development, vol 141, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, (2004), PP 421-426.
8. Introduction to Column. (Online),URL:http://amitpatel745.topcities.com/index_files/study/column_care.pdf
9. Detectors used in HPLC (online)URL:http://wiki.answers.com/Q/What_detectors_are_used_in_HPLC
10. Detectors (online) ,URL:http://hplc.chem.shu.edu/NEW/HPLC_Book/Detectors/det_uvda.html
11. Detectors (online) ,URL:http://www.dionex.com/enus/webdocs/64842-31644-02_PDA-100.pdf
12. Detectors (online),URL:<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/8867705>
13. Detectors (online),URL:<http://www.chem.agilent.com/Library/applications/59643559.pdf>
14. Detectors (online),URL:<http://hplc.chem.shu.edu/new/hplcbook/detector>
15. Draft ICH Guidelines on Validation of Analytical Procedures Definitions and terminology. Federal Register, vol 60. IFPMA, Switzerland, (1995), PP 1126.
16. Code Q2B, Validation of Analytical Procedures; Methodology. ICH Harmonized Tripartite Guidelines, Geneva, Switzerland, (1996), PP 1- 8.
17. Introduction to analytical method validation (online), available from: URL: <http://www.standardbase.hu/tech/HPLC%20validation%20PE.pdf>.

19. Data elements required for assay validation, (online) available from: URL: <http://www.labcompliance.com/tutorial/methods/default.aspx>.
20. Snyder LR practical HPLC method development, 2nd edition. John Wiley and sons, New York, (1997), PP 180-182.
21. Skoog D A, West D M, Holler FJ: Introduction of analytical chemistry. Sounder college of publishing, Harcourt Brace college publishers. (1994), PP 1-5.